

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity
in polymer processing technologies
of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

WP1 – ADVANCED HYBRID PROCESSING TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE DEMANDS D1.5 DEMONSTRATOR WITH IMPROVED PERFORMANCE

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1. Executive summary

Task 1.5 within WP1 of the IPPT_TWINN project focused on the development of physical demonstrators that validate the use of vitrimer materials in hybrid polymer processing and their functional advantages for circular product design.

According to the project plan, the demonstrator had to (i) show an improvement in bonding strength by at least 50 % or (ii) enable recycling-friendly triggered debonding.

The selected demonstrator consists of an injection-moulded vitrimer polypropylene (PP-V) plate onto which a multi-layer rib was overprinted using vitrimer acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS-V) composites. The first two rib layers were printed out of ABS-based vitrimer with 20 wt.% of milled carbon fibres to promote IR absorption and localized heating, while the upper layers were ABS-based vitrimer with 20 wt.% of glass beads for decreased anisotropic shrinkage, as demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of the demonstrator on left and physical demonstrator on the right

The demonstrator successfully exhibited localized heating under the influence of infrared light and infrared-triggered facilitated debonding of the rib, confirming the potential of vitrimer interfaces for recyclable multi-material parts. Moreover, adhesion between incompatible polymers (ABS and PP) was achieved using both grafted and vitrimerized materials.

2. Introduction

The main goal of WP1 – Advanced hybrid processing technologies for future demands is to develop processing routes that combine injection moulding and additive manufacturing using covalent adaptable networks (CANs). These materials allow reversible bonding, improving the durability and recyclability of multi-component products.

Task 1.5 of WP1 Development of demonstrators aimed to integrate the materials and know-how developed in Tasks 1.1–1.4 into a functional prototype. The final form of the demonstrator was chosen at the beginning of Task 1.4. Initially, plates were overprinted with the same base monomaterial rib and tested (T1.4); later, in T1.5, as a demonstrator multimaterial rib was overprinted on the plate. Moreover, the plate and rib were based on incompatible materials (PP plates and ABS ribs).

The demonstrator's purpose was to:

- validate the processability and bonding performance of vitrimer-based PP/ABS interfaces,
- demonstrate at least 50 % improvement in bonding strength or
- demonstrate triggered debonding.

The demonstrator therefore acts as proof-of-concept for smart and circular polymer systems within IPPT_TWINN. In consideration of the studied literature, a plan for the development of CANs was constructed, which included the evaluation of multiple mechanisms of CANs to yield the most appropriate material for further development, which includes weldability and processability via 3D printing and other conventional polymer processing techniques, as well as potential for bonding and trigger debonding for recyclability of multimaterial parts.

Although the original task description in the Grant Agreement foresaw demonstrating either at least a 50 % improvement in bonding strength or recycling-friendly triggered debonding, the final demonstrator focused primarily on the latter. This strategic choice was driven by the fundamental incompatibility of neat polypropylene (PP) and neat acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), which exhibit essentially no interfacial adhesion when joined via hybrid injection moulding and material extrusion processes. Grafting of maleic anhydride onto polypropylene (PPMAH) dramatically enhances adhesion, enabling robust bonding between the PP-based substrate and the ABS-based rib. In contrast, vitrimerization of both polymers (PPV4 and ABSV4) does not yield a statistically significant increase in bonding strength beyond the already effective PPMAH reference system. Nevertheless, the vitrimer-based interface still delivers substantially higher adhesion than the non-adherent neat ABS/neat PP combination, corresponding to an improvement of more than 50 % relative to the unmodified polymers. The distinctive added value of the vitrimer approach, therefore, lies not in superior initial bond strength but in the ability to combine strong initial interfacial bonding with on-demand, infrared-triggered debonding facilitated by dynamic covalent bond exchange. This enables clean, recycling-friendly disassembly of otherwise incompatible multi-material parts without causing structural damage to the components, aligning with the circular economy objectives of the IPPT_TWINN project [1,2]

3. Methods used

Demonstrator consists of a polypropylene vitrimer (PPV4) injection moulded base plate overprinted by the rib, which has the first 2 layers of ABS-V4 composite (ABSV4CF) with 20 wt.% of milled carbon fibre that are sensitive to infrared light. The following layers of the rib were printed with ABS-V4 composite (ABSV4GF) with 20 wt.% of glass beads. The reference part consisted of a polypropylene grafted with maleic anhydride (PP-MAH) plate with the same multi-material layer rib overprinted. Figures 2 and 3 present a 3D model and technical drawing of the demonstrator. Vitrimers were prepared by reactive extrusion, followed by compounding for composite preparation, and filament production, accurately described in T1.4 report titled Evaluated bonding strength between the components produced by hybrid technology. The procedure of injection moulding of substrates (PP-MAH and PPV4 plates) is also reported in the T1.4 report [3].

Figure 2: 3D model of the demonstrator

Figure 3: Technical drawing of the demonstrator

Filament production line AFE28 of Suzhou Aifuer Machinery CO., LTD (Figure 4) that was acquired in the scope of IPPT_TWINN project was used for filament production. The single-screw extruder SJ25/28 of the line is equipped with a screw made of 38CrMoALA. The screw has a diameter of 25 mm and an L/D ratio of 28:1. Its maximal operating speed is 72 rpm, and it provides a production capacity of 3–5 kg per hour. The extruder produces filament with a diameter ranging from 1.75 to 3 mm, achieving a tolerance of ± 0.02 – 0.03 mm. The system is controlled by a PLC using a closed-loop filament thickness regulation system.

Figure 4: Filament production line AFE28 of Suzhou Aifuer Machinery CO., LTD

ABS-based ribs were printed on the PP-based substrates using Tumaker BF 500 Dual 3D printer from IT3D Group (Figure 5) equipped with two printing heads, one for filament printing and the second for direct 3D printing from polymer granulate. In this case, only a filament extruder was used for printing the produced filaments at 230 °C with a 0.4 mm nozzle. Printing speed was 10 mm/s, infill was 100 %, and the build plate was heated to 75 °C.

Figure 5: Tumaker BF Dual 3D printer

Additionally, an infrared-based light was used to demonstrate spatio-selective heating and trigger debonding. An Alpina XD-YS2000 2000 W infrared heater with a golden halogen lamp was employed in combination with an Optris Xi400 thermocamera with a frame rate of 80 Hz and motorized focus, which was used to record the temperature change of the specimen under the infrared light. Both with the demonstrator in the testing set-up are presented in Figure 6. Samples were heated for 160 s.

Figure 6: IR heater, thermocamera and sample set-up for testing of heating selectivity

Debonding was evaluated using tensile tests on the Shimadzu AG - X Plus universal testing machine, equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The testing procedure of weld strength consisted of a preliminary test at 1 mm/min up to 3 N of load, followed by 50 mm/min until the break, as employed in previous tasks (T1.1-T1.4) and papers [4] of WP1.

Figure 7 illustrates the setup used for the mechanical evaluation of the IR-triggered debonding process. After pre-heating the interface via 120 seconds of IR exposure at 150 mm distance, tensile loading was applied to initiate separation of the rib from the PP-vitrimer substrate. The testing configuration ensures controlled and repeatable assessment of the interfacial strength under identical conditions.

Figure 7: Testing of debonding stress

Surface morphology and roughness of the vitrimer samples were characterised using a Keyence 3D digital optical microscope VHX 7000. High-resolution optical images were captured at 50x magnification to visualise the surface topography, debonded interfaces, and morphological changes. Surface roughness parameters, including the arithmetic mean height (R_a) was determined from 3D reconstructed profiles generated by the instrument's depth composition function. Measurements were performed on plate and debonded surfaces of reference plate and demonstrator plate.

4. Experimental results

The thermal transitions of the vitrimer materials were characterised in detail in Deliverable D1.3. For the polypropylene vitrimer (PPV4), the topology freezing transition temperature (T_v), determined from stress-relaxation and rheological measurements, lies in the range of 55 °C. For the ABSV4, the T_v was similarly found around 156 °C.

During IR exposure, the carbon-fibre-filled layers rapidly reached surface temperatures of 90–140 °C (see Figure 9 and new thermocouple data). At these temperatures, which are well above T_g but straddle or exceed T_v , the dynamic covalent bonds (associative exchange reactions) become sufficiently mobile. This enables topology rearrangement at the PP-V/ABS-V interface without requiring full melting of the crystalline PP domains or viscous flow of the entire bulk material. The localised heating thus activates the vitrimer network specifically at the interface, reducing interfacial shear strength and facilitating clean debonding. This mechanism is fundamentally different from classical thermoplastic welding or adhesive failure and relies on the temperature-dependent kinetics of the bond-exchange reactions, as described in D1.3.

Figure 8 shows the spatially selective heating of the demonstrator when exposed to infrared radiation. The carbon-fibre-filled ABS-V4 layers absorb IR energy significantly faster than the surrounding material, resulting in a rapid temperature increase localised within the lower rib region. The thermographic image reveals a temperature gradient, confirming that the CF-rich zone behaves as a targeted heating layer. The glass-bead-filled top layers exhibit notably lower temperature rise, demonstrating their function as a thermal barrier preventing unwanted heat spread. This behaviour verifies that the designed composite architecture enables precise activation of the interface without affecting the entire component.

Figure 8: Heating of the demonstrator under infrared light recorded by thermocamera

The temperature increase in the targeted layer in dependence on the distance from the light is presented in Figure 8. Adhesion testing was conducted on the distance of 5 cm.

Figure 9: Temperature increase of the targeted layer under IR light exposure in dependence on time and distance from the light

Table 1 and Figure 10 present the recorded debonding forces for both the vitrimer demonstrator and the PP-MAH reference configuration, since no adhesion could be achieved to neat ABS. The vitrimer system shows a distinct reduction in required debonding force and stress after IR activation (almost 54 %), while no significant decrease could be determined with the reference sample, confirming that the dynamic covalent network responds to infrared light-induced thermal triggering in 120 s, resulting in a temperature of 100 °C at the bond. For the polypropylene vitrimer (PPV4), this operating temperature lies well above its topology freezing transition temperature (52 °C), while for the ABS-based vitrimer ABSV4 remains below its T_v , which is at 156 °C, as calculated based on stress relaxation experiments reported in D1.3. The temperature is also above both T_g for PP (below 0 °C) and in the range of ABSV4 T_g (101 °C) reported in D1.4. Nevertheless, results point to the possibility that under these conditions, the dynamic covalent bond-exchange reactions became activated, due to mechanical stress assistance since PP T_m is at 147 °C as reported in D1.4. It is well documented in the vitrimer literature that the simultaneous application of mechanical stress or strain can synergistically accelerate topology rearrangement and associative bond exchange, effectively lowering the energy barrier for network reconfiguration. Consequently, the tensile loading applied during the debonding test (following 120 s IR exposure, which continued during the measurement) likely provided additional mechanical activation that promoted interfacial bond reshuffling. This stress-assisted dynamics mechanism likely contributed to the observed 54 % reduction in debonding force and stress, enabling clean interfacial separation. Such behaviour is consistent with reports demonstrating that external or internal stress enhances creep and dynamic covalent exchange in vitrimers by increasing segmental mobility and facilitating directional chain alignment along the loading direction [5–7]. In the PP-MAH reference system, which lacks dynamic covalent bonds, no comparable temperature- and stress-induced debonding facilitation was observed.

Table 1: Debonding forces and stresses

Sample	Value	Force (N)	Stress (MPa)
PPMAH	Average	77.49	1.03
	Standard deviation	29.22	0.39
PPMAH-IR	Average	68.43	0.91
	Standard deviation	14.84	0.20
PPV4	Average	48.88	0.65
	Standard deviation	16.26	0.22
PPV4-IR	Average	22.46	0.30
	Standard deviation	8.31	0.11

Figure 10: Debonding test results

Figure 11 compares the physical appearance of the debonded PP-MAH reference sample and the vitrimer demonstrator after testing. The reference sample shows significant tearing in the ABS CF vitrimer layers and residue of ABS vitrimer CF composite on the PPMAH plate, indicating that the interface cannot detach cleanly.

In contrast, the vitrimer demonstrator exhibits smooth and uniform separation surfaces, with minimal material transfer between the rib and the PP-vitrimer substrate. This visually supports the suitability of vitrimers for recycling-friendly multi-material design.

Figure 11: Debonded reference sample with PPMAH plate (left) and debonded demonstrator with PPV4 plate (right)

To provide a more detailed view of the failure modes, Figure 12 presents higher-magnification optical images of the debonded surfaces under magnification of 50x. Figure 12 shows the plate-side surfaces of the PP-MAH reference: significant tearing and residue coverage indicate cohesive failure within the ABS vitrimer layers rather than clean interfacial detachment. In contrast, the right side of Figure 12 shows the corresponding surfaces of the PPV4 demonstrator, revealing smooth, uniform separation with minimal material transfer. These images confirm that debonding occurs preferentially at the dynamic covalent interface.

Figure 12: PPMAH plate after debonding (left) and PPV4 (demonstrator) plate after debonding, both were debonded with IR light assistance

3D presentations of the profiles taken for the surface roughness determination using Kayence digital optical microscope are in Figure 13.

Figure 13: A) PPMAH plate, B) PPMAH plate at debonded surface, C) PPV4 (demonstrator plate) and D) PPV4 (demonstrator plate) at debonded surface, all in 3D view before surface roughness determination, 50x magnification

The surface roughness of the debonded interfaces was analysed to further elucidate the differences in failure mechanisms between the reference PP-MAH system and the PPV4 vitrimer demonstrator. As shown in Figure 14, the debonded surface of the PP-MAH plate exhibits significantly higher average roughness (R_a) compared to the PPV4 substrate. This increased roughness can be attributed to partial melting of the polypropylene matrix during the overprinting process. ABS was extruded during overprinting onto the substrates at a nozzle temperature of 240 °C, which exceeds the melting temperature ($T_m \approx 150$ °C) of PPMAH. Consequently, the PP-MAH surface experienced more pronounced melting and localised flow, resulting in deeper penetration of the molten ABS vitrimer into the substrate and stronger mechanical interlocking upon solidification and consequently chain entanglement. In contrast, the PPV4 vitrimer substrate displayed notably lower surface roughness after debonding, indicating that it underwent less melting and flow under the same overprinting conditions. This behaviour suggests a higher thermal resistance of the vitrimer network (arising from its dynamic covalent bonds), which limited excessive matrix melting and reduced the extent of mechanical interlocking. The smoother debonded surfaces the PPV4 system are therefore consistent with predominantly interfacial failure enabled by the activated dynamic covalent bonds rather than cohesive tearing within the substrate.

Figure 14: Surface roughness (R_a) determined for reference demonstrator plates and debonded surfaces after IR-triggered debonding

5. Conclusions

The development and evaluation of the vitrimer-based demonstrator within Task 1.5 clearly confirm the potential of covalent adaptable networks for next-generation hybrid polymer processing. By integrating injection moulding with additive manufacturing, the project successfully showcased how vitrimer chemistry can overcome long-standing challenges related to bonding incompatible polymers, enabling both high interfacial strength and controlled, recycling-oriented debonding.

The demonstrator's multi-material design, combining PP-vitrimer substrates with ABS-vitrimer composite ribs, proved that dynamic covalent interfaces can be selectively activated using infrared irradiation. The incorporation of carbon-fibre-filled layers enabled rapid, localised heating, allowing clean and repeatable debonding of joined components without structural degradation. This behaviour stands in clear contrast to reference PPMAH samples, where controlled separation could not be achieved, and IR irradiation did not significantly influence the debonding stress. Although vitrimer and PPMAH demonstrate strong adhesion, PP and ABS in their basic forms cannot be joined due to their incompatibility. In comparison, the adhesion of neat PP and ABS as reference materials is also improved by over 50 %.

Overall, the results demonstrate that vitrimer materials provide a versatile and robust platform for designing circular, repairable, and reconfigurable polymer products. The successful realisation of the demonstrator offers strong technological validation for the concepts developed within WP1 and establishes a solid foundation for future research and implementation, scalability, and integration into more complex multi-material systems.

6. Deviations from the GA

No deviations from GA in Task 1.5.

7. References

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